

Indonesia's Cooperation Effort with Interpol in Eradicating Illegal Fishing

Yulia Putri Rahmawanti¹, Satria Rizaldi Alchatib², Ganjar
Widhiyoga³

¹(Department of International Relations/Universitas Slamet Riyadi Surakarta)

²(Department of International Relations/Universitas Slamet Riyadi Surakarta)

³(Department of International Relations/Universitas Slamet Riyadi Surakarta)

ABSTRACT : This study aims to identify the cooperation effort carried out by Interpol during the administration of President Joko Widodo, with the main goal of improving Indonesia's maritime industry by realizing Indonesia to become the world's maritime center. However, in realizing the expectation, the illegal fishing issue must be resolved. Illegal fishing or illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing is a transnational crime that uses foreign vessels. IUU fishing is not a new issue, as the crime is organized and planned. IUU fishing cases that often occur in Indonesia, other than fish theft, are absence of documents and permits, violation of requirements for fishing equipment, port of call, document falsification, requirement manipulation, offshore transshipment, and double flagging. The illegal activities are not only Indonesia's problem but also a cross-border problem. In this study, the author wants to identify how the Indonesian government and Interpol cooperate to handle the IUU Fishing issue. The author uses international security theory with the concept of maritime security and international organization theory. This study uses a qualitative research method, as it was done in a natural situation.

KEYWORDS –Illegal, Unreported, Unregulated (IUU) Fishing, Interpol, World Maritime Center.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is the world's biggest archipelagic country that is acknowledged internationally without using its military force. Indonesia consists of 70% water area and 30% land area. The surface area of Indonesia in different islands reaches 1.92 million km². Indonesia's waters are far wider than its land. Indonesia's waters have a coastline of 18,000km, territorial waters of 12 miles with an area of 3.1 million km², and an economic exclusive zone of 200 miles with an area of 2.7 million km². With the area of waters, Indonesia is well-known as a maritime country (Sulistiyono, 2016). Indonesia's maritime industry has the potential to become a source of welfare for its nation. Therefore, President Joko Widodo sets a plan to turn Indonesia into the world's maritime center to improve Indonesia's maritime industry for public welfare and prosperity, equal economic development, and secure maritime industry in Indonesia. President Joko Widodo emphasized his plan to make Indonesia become the world's maritime center in the 2014 presidential election campaign, and the plan has become the national development plan. In order to encourage Indonesia to become the world's maritime center, the government designs infrastructure for the sea toll program, such as ports, navigation equipment, and

transport ships, to eradicate every problem and build a smooth logistics flow across Indonesia (Yayan M. Yani, 2015).

The implementation of Joko Widodo's administration policy triggered reactions from countries inside and outside Southeast Asia (Nainggolan, 2020). In his speech in front of the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR) on October 20, 2014, he said, "We have been too long turning our back on the sea, ocean, and bay. Now, it's the time for us to take back everything to achieve "*JalasvevaJayamahe*", we are glorious on the sea, we can realize our motto from the past." (Junef, 2019). In order to achieve the country's goal, whether it's short-term or long-term, Joko Widodo's administration also sets the Nawacita or the nine main priorities program to protect and provide security to the nation through a free and active foreign policy, reliable national security in the national development to strengthen Indonesia's identity as a maritime country. Through the Nawacita, the ministers in President Joko Widodo's cabinet make policies in the form of action programs, just like the program of the Minister of Maritime and Fisheries, Susi Pudjiastuti, followed by the other policymakers in the administration, especially the Indonesian Navy (Junef, 2019).

In realizing Indonesia's goal to become the world's maritime center, there is one serious issue that must be resolved first, which is illegal fishing. Illegal fishing or illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing (IUUF) is a form of a transnational crime that includes fish theft or taking Indonesian sea resources without permit, using foreign vessels, and even smuggling drugs that can be done within the crime (Nainggolan, 2020). The realization of the world's maritime center goal will depend on the eradication of IUUF, as IUUF disadvantages Indonesia in many sectors, such as maritime, economy, food, and energy (MTH, 2016). In order to fight against IUUF, the Indonesian government upholds the law in an assertive way by sinking, bombing, and burning foreign vessels that entered Indonesian waters illegally. The policy is one of President Joko Widodo's strategies to give a deterrent effect to other countries and show that Indonesia is serious in defending its territorial sovereignty. President Joko Widodo upholds the law on territorial waters through the synergy of economic and security strategies in the World Maritime Center policy (Syahrin, 2018).

IUUF cases in Indonesia can be considered as a part of transnational crime as it is organized and planned. The illegal fishing perpetrators set a plan to commit the crime and even paid attention to the cause and effects on every country where they committed the crime. Therefore, it is challenging to eradicate the crime if there's no international cooperation between countries or international organizations that are capable of fighting against the crimes. This matter is essential because it could make the eradication process easier for every party. The presence of transnational crime in illegal fishing makes Indonesia need international partnership to handle it. Thus, Indonesia partners with one of the international organizations, the International Criminal Police Organization (ICPO) or well-known as Interpol. The organization is one of the international police institutions that has a duty to uphold the law against transnational and international crimes (Inayati, 2019).

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

- **Theories of International Security**

International security is an effort of a party or international agency to protect the values and interests of a country and secure the safety of the nation. International security exists as there's a discussion about a way or system to protect a country from different threats, both external and internal threats. Alex Bellamy defines, "Security is a relative freedom from war, coupled with a relatively high expectation that defeat will not be a consequence of any war that should occur." According to Williams in 2003, security is an extreme and extraordinary matter with a situation that causes inconvenience that could disadvantage and take one's life (Barry Buzan, 2009).

International security studies have been improving as a main approach to understanding the driving forces in international politics. The subject matter of international security lies in the political interactions of those with interests in managing the security of individuals (Bakry, 2022). Security is the main issue for the realism class that causes a state security dilemma in taking defensive or offensive action, as no one knows the goal and purpose of other countries. Therefore, the balance of power system exists to create state security and stability because there is no domination between countries (Anugrah, 2017). International security has a significant difference before and after the Cold War, starting from the discussed issues to the methods used in discussing the issues. After the Cold War, security tends to consider 'subjectivity' aspects of individuals. As for the discussed issue, some new issues are starting to come up, such as the environment, poverty, terrorism, natural disaster, transnational crimes, and many others (Bakry, 2022). Due to a broader range of security, new threats also exist. One of them is terrorism and threats in the cyber world, which is well-known as cyber security. Terrorism is a serious threat that existed after the Cold War and is driven by the difference in ideology that transforms into a common threat of terrorism. The other threat is known as 'the nature of threats' or military threats, where the security issue becomes more comprehensive as it involves the aspects of the economy, social, culture, and even democratic issues and human rights (Azizah, 2020).

The approach or dominant paradigm that becomes mainstream in the study of international security is the realism perspective. From this perspective, the focus on security is limited. M. Walt (1991) stated that security is a study on war phenomena. Walt's approach is known as a traditional security or conventional security. On the other hand, the pluralism perspective sees security issues in a broader and more varied way. The significance of security is developing, not only focused on military aspects but also non-military aspects that are known as non-traditional security. Non-traditional security issues are varied in different areas but are connected, just like maritime security (Sagena, 2013).

Maritime security is commonly defined as a transnational responsibility, as it focuses on the significance of international cooperation and considers that maritime security is the responsibility of all parties. The United Nations (UN) discussed maritime security for the first time in the Informal Consultative Process (ICP) forum from 2001 to 2008. In the forum, the UN released reference documents related to threats against international peace and security from the sea. The UN had a challenge in formulating the concept of maritime security, as the UN avoided pre-emptive measures against maritime security forums outside the UN mechanism. Most of the issues are threats to natural resources and crimes against humanity. Therefore, strong regulations and clear international policy are needed to create shared security (Sudirman, 2016). Threats to maritime security are transnational, and the criminals operate cross-border, making maritime security not only having transnational consequences but also transcending maritime territory boundaries, where every security practice always includes nations and jurisdictions (Keliat, 2009).

Threats to maritime security are also evolving and creating new threats, not only military threats but also non-military, such as terrors that may impact the social, economic, and political situation, which also impact the relation between countries (Zaini, 2020). There are two ways to counter threats to maritime security. The first is direct bilateral diplomacy that focuses on conflict resolution, and the second is developing regional cooperation mechanisms that focus on creating consultative arrangements for maritime development and management (Keliat, 2009).

Based on the explanations above, it can be concluded that international security has two different perspectives, so it causes more varied threats and strongly impacts a country's stability. In order to counter the threats, the government must protect and synergize the national interests through international forums so it could be the national power, and strengthen the diplomacy efforts with quality and political communication skills.

- **Theories of International Organization**

An international organization is a membership or collectivity of independent entities in an organized team that aims to create sustainability based on an agreement of member countries (Sulaiman, 2009). The policy that regulates international organizations is recorded in the historical records of UN establishment in the Dumbarton Oaks Conference in 1944, which proposed a formulation of 50 UN charter draft articles. The international organization law developed by the UN and the UN General Assembly on October 24, 1970, in Res. 2625 (XXV), stipulates that member countries of an international organization are responsible for carrying out the decision taken by the international organization, including recommendations, appeals, and requests (Cornelez, 2018).

According to Daniel S. Cheever and H. Field Haviland Jr, international organization is a setting in the form of international cooperation that is institutionalized between countries, which is based on an agreement to carry out the functions that give benefits or mutual cooperation through meetings and periodic activities of the members. Meanwhile, Jackson and Sorensen see international organization as an individual that acts as a party that has the authority to formulate, define, and present certain problems to others. International organization also acts as a problem-solving contributor by offering solutions to others (Sorensen, 2013).

According to Clive Archer, an international organization has three roles, an instrument to achieve the interest of member countries, a vessel or forum to carry out diplomacy, formulate, and initiate the establishment of international agreements, and an independent individual that can stand alone without the influence of outer force. Meanwhile, J. Samuel Barkin stated that international organization is also used as an agent of member countries to promote and protect themselves from globalization forces. Barkin admits that international organization has an overpowering role, but an international organization is still an agent of countries and can not replace a country (Archer, 2001).

Based on the opinions of some experts above, an international organization can be defined as a meeting forum to build relations between countries to achieve the common interest of the members in the forum. Besides that, an international organization acts as a vessel for its member countries to cooperate based on their expertise and roles.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology carried out in this study is a qualitative approach with a descriptive method. A qualitative research methodology is an approach where the researcher collects study data through face-to-face interviews, or interacts with the source person directly. This research methodology is also known as a naturalistic research methodology. The purpose of this methodology is to describe the current phenomena to give an idea about the existing condition (Creswell, 2010). According to Sugiyono (2007:1), qualitative research methodology is research on a natural object where the researcher acts as the key instrument, with collective data collection, inductive data analysis, and research result that emphasizes more on the meaning than generalization.

The data collection technique used in this study uses primary and secondary data sources. The primary data collection is done through an interview to learn and complete the right and accurate data. In this study, the author interviewed the Head of the Interpol International Products Subdivision as a source person. As for the secondary data, the data collection is done with an in-depth assessment of study documents by reading and browsing information related to the study on the internet. In this study, the author uses secondary data sources following the law, books, journals, and articles related to the study topic. The data analysis methodology is done qualitatively and comprehensively, which results in empirical facts.

IV. RESULTS

- **Illegal fishing as a threat to world maritime security**

Based on *de facto*, the IUUF issue has been attracting the attention of regional and world organizations as a form of transnational organized crime that causes the state to suffer losses and threatens the sustainability of marine resources. Fishery holds an essential and strategic role in the economic development of every country, especially in income distribution and improving the nation's standard of living. The rampant IUUF could impact the global fishery dynamics, such as the global fish consumption that keeps increasing and fishing grounds in other countries that keep diminishing. The issue forces fishing operators to operate illegally without complying with the applied regulations. The United Nations Convention of Law (UNCLOS) 1982 regulates every country to pay attention to the rights of other countries in carrying out every activity and international freedom rights according to the terms formulated by the convention and other conditions in international law. Article 82 of UNCLOS 1982 on fishing freedom mentions that freedom does not mean handing over power to other countries but freedom for protection and not damaging the waters and marine resources (Hadju, 2021).

According to UNCLOS 1982, the activities categorized as IUUF are as follows:

1. Fishing in the territorial waters or exclusive economic zone of another country or not having a permit from the country (illegal fishing).
2. Fishing in the territorial waters or exclusive economic zone of another country and not complying to the terms applied in the country (unregulated fishing).
3. Fishing in the territorial waters or exclusive economic zone of another country and not reporting the operational activities or data of vessels and the catch (unreported fishing).

The 2001 International Plan of Action to Prevent, Deter and Eliminate IUU Fishing (IPOA-IUU Fishing) explained about fishing activities that considered as IUUF, which are as follows:

1. Fishing activities carried out by individuals or foreign vessels in the waters that become jurisdiction of a country without any permit from the country or against the law and regulations.
2. Fishing activities carried out by vessels that raise a flag of a country that become a member of a regional fishery management organization, but carried out in a way that violates the regulations on management and conservation of resources adopted by the organization, where the regulations bind the countries that become the members, or against the other relevant international law.
3. Fishing activities that violate the national law or international responsibilities, including the responsibilities of member countries of a regional fishery management organization to the organization.
4. Fishery crime that commonly occurs in Indonesia's fishing ground is fish theft by foreign fishing vessels, especially vessels from neighboring countries.

Therefore, the activities that are categorized as Unreported Fishing are as follows:

1. Unreported fishing activities or reported inappropriately to the national authority in ways that violate the law and regulations.
2. Fishing activities that are conducted in the area of Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO) competence that are unreported or reported inappropriately in ways contrary to the reporting procedures of the organization.

Meanwhile, what is meant by fishing activities that are viewed as Unregulated Fishing are:

1. Fishing activities that are conducted in a relevant RFMO area that are carried out by vessels without nationality, or vessels that hoisted the flag of a country that is not a member of the organization or a fishing company that carried out its fishing activities in ways contrary to the conservation and management arrangements of the organization,
2. Fishing activities carried out in territorial waters where there are no applicable conservation and management arrangements that are carried out in ways that are contrary to the country's responsibilities to conserve and manage marine natural resources in accordance with the provisions of international law.

- **The Threat of Illegal Fishing in Indonesian Waters**

Indonesia is an archipelagic country that is rich in fish and marine biota resources. This has made Indonesia one of the countries where IUUF activities are rife. IUUF issues carried out by foreign parties do not only concern damage and loss of fishery resources, but also violations of a country's sovereignty over the management of marine resources they own. As if they are untouchable, foreign ships that carried out these prohibited actions easily enter and leave Indonesian territorial waters, even considering Indonesian waters to be their traditional fishing territory (Bendar, 2015). The rise of IUUF in Indonesia can be influenced by several factors. The first factor is the weak management of marine resources by the government and the relevant authorities. The second factor is related to the human resources of Indonesian fishermen, who still have limited abilities in exploiting the fishery potentials available in Indonesian waters. The next factor, because Indonesia does not have enough KKP patrol boats, there is a lack of intensive surveillance in Indonesian seas.

Indonesian waters are vulnerable to IUUF activities as the geographical location of the country's waters is in border waters close to international waters, so it is very open for IUUF criminals to carry out their actions (Muhamad, 2012). Based on the statement of Prof. Jems in a teleconference lecture held by University of North Carolina in collaboration with Indonesian Fisheries, KLH and UGM Environment, the IUUF actors are brave. Prof. Jems said the perpetrators really understand the entry and distribution of fish and other marine biota, so they would carry out their action after calculating the gains and losses; the losses would not be as large as the profits. If successful, the benefits would multiply (Bendar, Amin, 2015). In the context of maritime security, IUUF's activities in Indonesian territorial waters are an issue that must be looked into and can become a source of problems between IUUF actors and the Government of Indonesia, which can result in a relationship problem with the country of the IUUF actors. It can be concluded that IUUF activities can have an impact on relations between nations and pose a threat to a State's stability. Therefore, maximum eradication efforts are need to overcome this problem.

The IUUF practices that occurred in Indonesia are serious crimes as the perpetrators would continue to improve and take advantage of their status given by their fishing vessel permits. These crimes are highly organized and fall into the category of "Crimes Related to Fisheries" (Rini, 2020). The Law in 2009 that revised the Law issued in 2004 explains how fishing should be done so as not to damage the environment or marine ecosystems in Indonesia, namely:

- a. Use of appropriate fishing gear and permitted by the government
- b. Ships that are permitted must have met all the technical requirements
- c. Notification of the maximum limit of fish caught with several examples of small fish that are not yet fit for consumption
- d. Must understand the ins and outs of the area and the right season before fishing
- e. Does not cause damage to the marine ecosystem from the fishing activities
- f. New species of fish should not be caught. If caught, it is mandatory to be released back into the marine ecosystem

- g. Prioritize marine cultivation
- h. It is forbidden to throw pests into the sea that have the potential to damage fish
- i. And other requirements

IUUF crimes in Indonesia have been tried by the fisheries court since 2018. All the perpetrators were subject to imprisonment and fines. Even though it is stated in the law regarding illegal fishing crimes, the judges' rulings were contradictory to international legal instruments, namely the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) as, basically, the 1982 UNCLOS only prohibits the imposition of prison sentences on perpetrators of illegal fishing, as stipulated in Article 73 paragraph (3) UNCLOS, namely: "Coastal state penalties for violations of fisheries laws and regulations in the exclusive economic zone may not include imprisonment, in the absence of agreements to the contract by the state concerned, or any other form of corporal punishment". In setting other international norms, in accordance with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) Agreement to Promote Compliance with International Conservation and Management Measures by Fishing Vessels on the High Seas, it is explained that the agreement recorded in the agreement aims to prevent changes nationality of the flag of the ship on fishing vessels in the high seas under the flag of the ship state that is unable and does not wish to enforce international fisheries conservation and management measures. Maintenance of fishing vessel management and international cooperation is extensively managed through the provisions of this agreement (Rini, 2020).

- **Cooperation between Interpol and Polri to eradicate illegal fishing in Indonesian waters**

As a form of the Indonesian government's efforts to eradicate IUUF, President Joko Widodo has formed Task Force (Satgas) 115 through Presidential Regulation Number 115 of 2015, on 19 October 2015, to support law enforcement activities against crimes in the fisheries sector, especially illegal fishing. The goal of establishing Task Force 115 is to develop and implement effective and efficient law enforcement operations at sea in Indonesia by optimizing the use of personnel and operational equipment, including ships, aircraft and other technology owned by the Ministry of Marine and Fisheries, the National Police, the Attorney General's Office (AGO) and Bakamla (Octavian, 2019). The Task Force 115 comprises four state institutions, namely the Directorate General of Marine and Fisheries Resources Supervision, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (Ditjen PSDKP-KKP), the Indonesian National Navy (TNI-AL), the Directorate of Water Police (DitPolri) and the Maritime Security Agency (Bakamla). In carrying out its duties, Task Force 115 receives directions from the Coordinating Minister for Politics, Law and Security (Menkopolhukam), the Coordinating Minister for the Economy, the Coordinating Minister for Human Development and Culture, the Coordinating Minister for Maritime Affairs, the Commander of the Indonesian National Armed Forces, the Indonesian National Police Chief and the Attorney General's Office (Esperansa, 2020) .

In addition, the Government of Indonesia cooperates with the International Criminal Police Organization (ICPO)-Interpol. To eradicate international crime, Interpol often circulates arrest orders to Interpol member countries to make it easier to find criminals and arrest them. In international cooperation, there are several paths available, such as police-to-police. This path can be taken if a nation has good relations with the state police of other nations that would be invited to cooperate. Indonesia was officially accepted as a member of the ICPO-Interpol through the Decree of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Indonesia No.245/PM/1954 dated October 5, 1954, the Indonesian Government sent the Bureau of the State Police as the Indonesian National Central Bureau (NCB) to represent the Government of Indonesia in the ICPO organization -Interpol and Head of the Indonesian National Police (Kapolri) as Head of the NCB (Interpol, n.d.).

In an interview on September 12, 2022, at the NCB-Interpol Jakarta Office, AKBP Norman Sitindaon emphasized that, in carrying out his duties, Interpol does not have the authority to conduct investigations and makes arrests in criminal cases as Interpol is not a law enforcement agency. Instead, Interpol is an international organization. Interpol only maximizes efforts to facilitate the provision of information when international or

transnational crimes occur. The system implemented by NCB-Interpol Indonesia is currently a breakthrough through the I-24/7 Global Police Communication System. This system is a connected communication system in 190 member countries of Interpol to share information about crime and criminal activity 24 hours a day, 7 days a week (Indonesia, 2007). In handling cases of illegal fishing through its delegation to ask member countries of the United Nations (UN), which was conveyed by the Minister of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs, Susi Pudjiastuti, at the United Nations Maritime Conference: Transnational Organized Crime in Fisheries Industry with Norway, Interpol and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) in New York (Rini, 2020).

Indonesia and Interpol have collaborated to deal with illegal fishing cases after signing a memorandum of understanding (MoU). In addition, to strengthen cooperation between Indonesia and Interpol. On December 15, 2021, the Ministry of Marine and Fishery has signed a cooperation agreement with the International Relations Division (Divhubinter) of the National Police regarding the utilization of the Interpol I-24/7 network, which is Interpol's global communication network known as the Interpol Global Police Communication System (IGCS). This agreement is known as the Interpol Agreement (Hidayat, 2021). In dealing with illegal fishing cases, Interpol has launched a program called Project Scale in 2013 in Lyon, France. The program is a global initiative to detect, suppress and eradicate fishing crimes. The program is funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD) and The Pew Charitable Trusts. Basically, this program aims to support its member countries to be more effective in overcoming crimes in the exploitation of the world's natural resources (Interpol, 2019).

AKBP Norman Sitindaon also explained that the Project Scale formed by Interpol was a program that had not been completed or was still being followed up as no data had been prepared. Within five years after Project Scale was launched, the project changed its name to Interpol Global Fisheries Enforcement, whose mission was to assist member countries in increasing awareness and capability in investigations, which aims to identify and dismantle criminal networks related to the fishing industry. In carrying out its mission, Interpol Global Fisheries Enforcement is supported by the Interpol Fisheries Crime Working Group (FCWG), which provides an international platform for cooperation between member countries (Interpol, 2018). The FCWG is led by the Governments of Norway, Indonesia and Fiji, under the guidance of a criminal research development expert who is one of Interpol's top officials. Indonesia hosted a conference held by FCWG on 6-8 October 2016 in Yogyakarta. Interpol also assists Indonesia in forming the National Environmental Security Task Forces (NEST), which consists of the police, customs, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) and the prosecutor's office who work together to maintain national security (AryuniYuliantiningsih, 2021).

Indonesia has also carried out cooperation that was participated by countries at the regional level, as well as international organizations, such as FAO, UNODC and Interpol. The cooperation is known as the Regional Cooperation Agreement Against Crimes Related to Fisheries. In 2004, written in the International Maritime Bureau (IMB), there were three regions that experienced the highest number of maritime crimes, namely Indonesia, the Malacca Strait and Singapore (Maulidy, 2011). Therefore, the formation of this cooperation aims to enforce the law against crimes in the field of fisheries to protect fishery resources of Indonesia, as recorded in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This collaboration was organized by Indonesia for the first time in the form of a conference on May 19, 2016, which was named the Regional Conference to Establish a Regional Convention Against IUUF and Its Related Crimes. During the conference, a classification of international organizations was formed that would collaborate in handling IUUF cases. Interpol itself has cooperated with FAO to address law enforcement issues, which will be able to determine the instruments for its implementation (Rini, 2020).

To follow up on the first conference, another conference was held which was held on 18-19 September 2017 in Jakarta. During the conference, a Technical Working Group was formed to conduct an analysis of the concept of IUUF and crimes related to fisheries, and the preparation of instruments related to fisheries. This conference is fully supported by FAO, UNODC and Interpol, chaired by H.E Arif Havas Oegroseno, Deputy for

Maritime Sovereignty Coordination at the Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs (Ambari, 2017). This conference provides advantages in the aspect of international cooperation in the field of law and the success of this collaboration will be a 'super diplomacy' for Indonesia to change the perception of countries that view the fisheries sector as a fisheries management regime, capable of achieving a crime regime so that all countries must obey and submit according to predetermined rules (Rini, 2020). The context of international organizations in the efforts to eradicate IUUF are efforts that require good coordination between member countries to jointly address this problem. In eradicating IUUF, several international organizations, namely Interpol, FAO, UNODC, held a cooperation negotiation in the Regional Cooperation Agreement Against Crimes Related to Fisheries. It can be concluded that IUUF is a crime that can ruin relations between countries, with the existence of an international organization it is a collaborative initiative that is considered to have a strategy for solving problems by equating ideas for discussions and strengthening diplomacy.

V. CONCLUSION

IUUF activities are rife in Indonesia due to several factors. The first factor that can be explained is the weak management of marine resources by the government and the relevant authorities, The second factor regards the human resources, particularly the Indonesian fishermen, who still have limited abilities in exploiting fishery potentials in Indonesian waters. The next factor, Indonesia lacks KKP's patrol boats, which has caused the lack of intensive surveillance in Indonesian seas. Efforts have been made by Indonesia, including the formation of Task Force 115, which is an international cooperation with international police agencies, Interpol and regional cooperation which is participated by various countries and several international organizations. Interpol launched Project Scale, which changed to Interpol Global Fisheries Enforcement to identify and dismantle criminal networks associated with the fishing industry. To follow up on the first conference, another conference was held which was held on 18-19 September 2017 in Jakarta. During the conference, a Technical Working Group was formed to conduct an analysis of the concept of IUUF and crimes related to fisheries, and the preparation of instruments related to fisheries.

Indonesia has carried out cooperation that was participated by countries at the regional level, as well as international organizations such as FAO, UNODC and Interpol. This collaboration is known as the Regional Cooperation Agreement Against Crimes Related to Fisheries. The aim of this collaboration is to enforce crimes in the fisheries sector to protect fishery resources in Indonesia, as recorded in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As a form of Indonesia's contribution to this cooperation, Indonesia joined the Working Groups, which was formed to fight crimes in the fisheries sector.

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